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DEPENDENCE OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION DEVELOPMENT WITH THE LEVEL OF FREE AMINO ACIDS IN BLOOD SERUM

D.A. Rashidova

Abstract. *We were interested in the effect of glycine on the function of the cardiovascular system in normal and pathological conditions. For this purpose, a chromatographic analysis of free amino acids in the blood serum of patients with myocardial infarction was performed. The conducted correlation analysis showed the presence of a negative relationship between the level of troponin I and the content of free glycine in the blood with a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.29$. This shows the dependence of the degree of myocardial infarction on the level of the amino acid we studied - glycine.*

Key words: *amino acids, blood serum, myocardial infarction, troponin I, glycine, proline, lysine, chromatogram.*

ЗАВИСИМОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНФАРКТА МИОКАРДА С УРОВНЕМ СВОБОДНЫХ АМИНОКИСЛОТ В СЫВОРОТКЕ КРОВИ

Д.А. Рашидова.

Аннотация. *Нас интересовало влияние глицина на функцию сердечно-сосудистую систему в норме и при патологических состояниях. С этой целью был проведен хроматографический анализ свободных аминокислот сыворотки крови больных с инфарктом миокарда. Проведенный корреляционный анализ показал наличие между уровнем тропонина I и содержанием свободного глицина в крови отрицательной связи с коэффициентом корреляции $r = -0,29$. Что показывает зависимость степени инфаркта миокарда с уровнем, изученного нами аминокислоты – глицином.*

Ключевые слова: *аминокислоты, сыворотка крови, инфаркт миокарда, тропонин I, глицин, пролин, лизин, хроматограмма.*

MIOKARD INFARKTI RIVOJLANISHINING QON ZARDOBIDAGI ERKIN AMINOKISLOTALAR MIQDORIGA BOG'LIQLIGI

D.A. Rashidova

***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu ishda biz glitsinning normal va patologik holatlarda yurak qon-tomir tizimiga ta'sirini o'rganish qiziqirdi. Bu maqsadda miokard infarkti bilan og'riqan bemorlarning qon zardobidagi erkin aminokislotalar xromatografik tahlili o'tkazildi. O'tkazilgan korrelatsion tahlil troponin I va qondagi erkin aminokislotalar miqdori o'rtasida korrelatsiya koeffitsenti $r = -0,29$ ga teng bo'lgan manfiy bog'lanish borligini ko'rsatdi. Bu miokard infarkti darajasi va biz o'rgangan aminokislota – glitsinning qondagi miqdori o'rtasida bog'liqlik borligini ko'rsatadi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** aminokislotalar, qon zardobi, miokard infarkti, troponin I, glitsin, prolin, lizin, xromatogramma.*

Introduction: Amino acids are the basic building blocks of proteins. Amino acids are involved in vital processes of the body, including the synthesis of neurotransmitters and hormones (thyroid, catecholamines, serotonin, nitric oxide, melatonin), cell formation, tissue growth and regeneration, maintenance of muscle mass, immune functions, etc. We were interested in the effect of glycine on the cardiovascular system function in normal and pathological conditions. Cardiomyocytes contain glycine-controlled chloride channels. In the work of X. Zhong et al. (2012), it was shown that intraperitoneal administration of glycine at a dose of 500 mg/kg to rats with experimental myocardial ischemia with subsequent reperfusion significantly reduces the size of the infarction (by 21%). According to the authors, this effect was associated with an increase in the ventricular ejection fraction [1,3,4]. It was also found that glycine inhibits platelet aggregation in in vitro studies, and increases bleeding time in rats fed a diet containing 2.5–5% glycine [2,5]. In the work of Y. Ding et al., a dependence of a decrease in the risk of heart attack on the concentration of glycine in blood plasma was demonstrated [3,6,7]. Most studies report on the effectiveness of glycine in various pathologies, although the doses used are quite high.

Materials and methods. The material for determining the amino acid composition of plasma were samples taken from patients with an established diagnosis of myocardial infarction in the acute period using the determination of Troponin I (Finecare FIA Meter Analyzer manufactured by Guangzhou Wondfo Biotech Co., Ltd., China) upon admission to the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Cardiology (RSSC). Also, blood of male donors of suitable ages was used as

samples for the control group. To isolate free amino acids from the patients' blood plasma, 1 ml of 20% TCAA was added to 1 ml of the test sample. After 10 min, the precipitate was separated by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 15 min. After separating 0.1 ml of the supernatant, it was lyophilized. The hydrolyzate was evaporated, the dry residue was dissolved in a mixture of triethylamine-acetonitrile-water (1:7:1) and dried. This operation was repeated twice to neutralize the acid. Phenylthiocarbonyl derivatives (PTC) of amino acids were obtained by reaction with phenylthioisocyanate according to the method of Steven A., Cohen Daviel. Identification of amino acid derivatives was performed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). HPLC conditions: Agilent Technologies 1200 chromatograph with DAD detector, 75x4.6 mm Discovery HS C18 column. Solution A: 0.14 M CH₃COONa + 0.05% TEA pH 6.4, B:CH₃CN. Flow rate 1.2 ml/min, absorption 269 nm. Gradient %B/min: 1-6%/0-2.5 min; 6-30%/2.51-40 min; 30-60%/40.1-45 min; 60-60%/45.1-50 min; 60-0%/50.1-55 min.

Results of the study. We conducted studies to study the amino acid spectrum of the blood of patients with myocardial infarction. For this purpose, blood was obtained from 8 patients admitted to the cardiology intensive care unit of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Cardiology with a diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction. The latter was diagnosed based on the determination of troponin I levels in the blood. The average troponin I level in the blood of the patients we studied was 27.55 ± 5.90 ng/ml, with fluctuations from 8.09 to 50.00 ng/ml. The reference values were less than 0.29 ng/ml. The blood of 8 male volunteers was used as a control.

The study showed that in myocardial infarction, statistically significant changes in the content of amino acids serine, threonine, proline, tyrosine, valine, histidine, isoleucine, leucine, tryptophan and phenylalanine compared to normal values were not observed. Of the 18 amino acids we studied, statistically significant ones were found in 8. The glycine content was found to be reduced by 39.7% of the normal value. Moreover, if the fluctuations of the values in the norm were within $69.80 \div 125.48$ mmol/l, then in myocardial infarction it was equal to $28.37 \div 92.18$ mmol/l. The asparagine content was found to be below the normal value by 48.9%. The fluctuations in values were $79.40 \div 142.14$ mmol/l in the norm and $29.52 \div 102.48$ mmol/l in myocardial infarction. The glutamine content in the blood in myocardial infarction was 80.6% lower than the normal value. The fluctuations in values in the norm were within $112.01 \div 355.73$ mmol/l, and in myocardial infarction $30.11 \div 135.48$ mmol/l. The cysteine content was also below normal (by 60.6%). If the fluctuations in the normal values were $103.75 \div 497.06$ mmol/l, then in case of a heart attack it was $44.24 \div$

129.42 mmol/l. The arginine content in the blood in case of a myocardial infarction was also below normal by 29%. In this case, the fluctuations in the normal values were $63.89 \div 195.58$ mmol/l, while in case of a myocardial infarction it was $55.74 \div 164.52$ mmol/l. The blood alanine content, unlike all other amino acids, was higher than 49.1% in myocardial infarction. The fluctuations in values were within the normal range of $18.18 \div 55.34$ mmol/l, and $40.63 \div 69.14$ mmol/l in myocardial infarction. The blood methionine content in myocardial infarction was also lower than the normal value by 57.4%, with fluctuations in values for the norm within $38.07 \div 411.10$ mmol/l and for myocardial infarction - $33.24 \div 124.79$ mmol/l.

In myocardial infarction, a significant decrease in lysine content compared to normal values was also observed (by 49.6%). The fluctuations in values were in the norm $30.30 \div 201.18$ mmol/l and in myocardial infarction - $30.99 \div 70.93$ mmol/l.

We were interested in the question of the dependence of the degree of myocardial infarction on the level of the amino acid we studied – glycine. The conducted correlation analysis showed the presence of a negative relationship between the level of troponin I and the content of free glycine in the blood with a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.29$.

In this case, the curve obtained during the study and the calculated regression curve almost completely coincided. The regression equation was as follows: $y = -0.20x + 66.21$.

Conclusion. Thus, the obtained results indicate the presence of a certain relationship between the development and degree of myocardial infarction with the level of free glycine in the blood serum. At lower values of the content of free glycine, a more severe course of acute myocardial infarction is observed.

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